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THE FACTORS INFLUENCING THE FORMING OF POLITICAL AWARENESS TOWARDS PARTICIPATING IN THE GENERAL NATIONAL ELECTIONS: A FIELD STUDY ON A SAMPLE OF THE STUDENTS OF THE BACHELOR'S DEGREE IN AL-ISTIQLAL UNIVERSITY, AN-NAJAH NATIONAL UNIVERSITY, HEBRON UNIVERSITY AND PALESTINE TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY - KADOORIE

Qusai A. Ibrahim^{1*} and Hasan Ali AlMadhani^{2*}

¹Associate Professor, Department of Psychology, Faculty of Humanities, Al-Istiqlal University, Jericho, Palestine. Email: qusai.ibrahim@pass.ps Orcid ID: 0000-0001-7540-2192

²Political advisor to the Arab Parliament, Sultanate of Oman. Email: hamadhani@hotmail.com

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Corresponding Author: Qusai A. Ibrahim & Hasan Ali Almadhani
(qusai.ibrahim@pass.ps, hamadhani@hotmail.com)

ABSTRACT

The study aimed to specify the factors influencing the forming of political awareness towards participating in the general national elections: A field study on a sample of the students of the Bachelor's degree in Al-Istiqlal University, An-Najah National University, Hebron University and Palestine Technical University - Kadoorie. Methods: This study belongs to the descriptive studies pattern by relying on the quantitative methodology. Due to the exceptional circumstances of the collective genocide campaign to which the Palestinian people are exposed to by the Zionist occupation which affected humans, trees and stones, and the Zionist-American war against Iran in 2026 A.D., this is considered as a challenge which is difficult to confront by the researchers in the various scientific and academic domains at the world level. Accordingly, the researcher conducted this study and applied it on an improbable sample by the available method. The sample of the study consisted of (412) participants from the students of the Bachelor's degree in in Al-Istiqlal University, An-Najah National University, Hebron University and Palestine Technical University - Kadoorie. Results: The results of the study showed that a percentage of 68.7% from the individuals of sample of the study have the desire to participate in the general national elections in Palestine in case these elections were conducted. The results of the study also indicated that the axes of the factors which influence the forming of the political awareness towards participating in the general national elections which are connected with the societal circumstances having a political stamp, and which are connected with the organizations of the civil society, and which are connected with the university, and which are connected with the individual were high, while the results were medium on the axes of the factors which influence the forming of the political awareness towards participating in the general national elections which are connected with the family. Conclusions: The study came with a number of recommendations, the most prominent of which is the necessity of reinforcing the role of the educational

institutions, especially the universities, for developing the political awareness among the students through including the concepts of political participation and the elections in the study curricula, in addition to activating the students' activities which give impetus to dialogue and constructive political discussion.

KEYWORDS: Political Awareness, Participation, Elections, Palestines

1. THE PROBLEM AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK OF THE STUDY

Human consciousness that is open to both the self and others serves as a benchmark for cultural advancement and progress; yet one finds no examples of it in the developments of modernity and the contemporary era, because open-minded consciousness is grounded in a cognitive framework based on a balance between reason and emotion. Among the tools for achieving this balance are: Criticism for the sake of construction and reform, and creativity for the sake of creating and composing elements of knowledge that contribute to the development of human societies (Jirjis & Abu Hajila, 2024). Consciousness is defined as a mental state characterized by a person's perception of the world through reason or emotion. Based on this, human consciousness manifests in various forms that differ according to the perceived domain or the object of consciousness, as humans experience diverse forms of consciousness, such as religious, scientific, political, and moral consciousness. From this perspective, it can be said that political consciousness is the state in which an individual or members of society engage with issues of political life in their various dimensions and adopt an emotional stance toward these issues (Maghazi, 2019).

Political awareness is a topic that has attracted widespread attention from scholars and researchers, particularly in the Arab region, due to their recognition of its role in equipping individuals to understand public systems and policies, government plans, and participation in the development of their societies—as one of the fundamental pillars upon which the social and political system is built. Ignoring it during the state-building process will almost certainly result in a weaker structure that will collapse in the face of any crisis affecting the state or civilization, regardless of the scale of political or demographic development (Ashour, 2023; Al-Khaza'leh & Lahiani, 2021).

The strength of a society's political awareness is a source of strength for the state's politics and political stability, as well as for its economic, cultural, and social development. Consequently, it unites members of society with state institutions in achieving common goals, helps avoid social problems and the waste of funds in social reform and development, and minimizes the material losses and various costs that the state incurs in addressing social issues (Ahmed & Abu Al-Qasim, 2017; Opeyemi, 2018). Political awareness refers to the level of young people's understanding of the political and historical reality of their society and their role in the political

process, including political orientations, organizational affiliations, and electoral behavior. Political awareness results in the ability to analyze events in a scientific and practical manner to eliminate many of the causes that hold societies back, such as extremism, poverty, and illiteracy (Zaki, 2024; Hermosa, 2021).

Political awareness plays a significant role in the issue of cultural renaissance, as the reality experienced by Middle Eastern societies is characterized by contradictions in certain fundamental concepts, and a clash between the old and the new, as well as a clash between the modern and the traditional and the overlap between them, leading to a cultural crisis that creates a conflict between the realization of identity and civilization and between heritage and modernity, and results in a disturbance in social consciousness. Awareness aids cultural renaissance, and this requires correcting one's self-awareness and understanding of social and political reality, because no cultural or intellectual renaissance can be achieved without linking history, the present, and the future. Cultural background is often linked to knowledge of historical events and their scientific analysis, followed by the development of future plans to instill sound civic concepts rooted in fundamental principles in the minds of the new generation, so that they, in turn, can bring about changes on the political, social, and economic fronts. Building political consciousness cannot be achieved all at once but requires several stages, and the conditions for these stages must be established to advance the political reality of society (Al-Mawla, 2019; Durban, et al., 2025). Furthermore, political awareness holds exceptional importance for peoples, as it embodies the essence of their civilization, and reflects the level and extent of their resilience and ability to confront any instances of cultural, intellectual, and political invasion. The strength of a society's political awareness is a source of strength for the state's politics and stability, as well as for its economic, cultural, and social development; it unites members of society with state institutions in achieving goals and addressing social issues (Hamdan & Bani Khalid, 2024).

Political awareness is closely linked to socialization; socio-political socialization is the process through which an individual acquires and develops his or her political views. There are various mechanisms and tools for political socialization, including the family, educational institutions, political parties, peer groups, religious institutions, and media organizations. The process of political socialization of citizens and the development of their

political awareness have become matters of great importance to which democratic states pay close attention and subject to extensive scientific study. Political socialization leads to the maturation of political awareness and the practice of political action. Through these scientific methods of political socialization, the government ensures that it gains public support for its democratic policies (Al-Farra, 2017; Azhar, et al., 2024). Political awareness is often linked to factors of social and political socialization, as socialization is one of the most fundamental pillars in shaping political awareness, which determines the nature of an individual's behavior and their view of themselves and the society in which they live (Mounis, 2019). Political awareness is also an important factor influencing participation in political processes. Research has shown that a higher level of political awareness—which includes knowledge of elections and politicians—is associated with improved political trust and participation. Studies have concluded that political awareness has a positive impact on political knowledge, which in turn leads to increased political participation (Al-Dulaimi et al., 2025; Zetra et al., 2022).

It is worth noting that the family is the first social group with which an individual interacts, and it serves as the primary framework within which they receive the foundations of their social and political upbringing. Numerous studies have confirmed that an individual's political orientation begins to take shape during the pre-school and pre-college years. An individual's personality is also shaped by the family through the freedoms the family allows its children—such as discussion, dialogue, expressing opinions, acceptance, and respect for others' views—or, conversely, through authoritarianism, coercion, negativity, and indifference (Al-Dulaimi & Al-Ta'an, 2024; Al-Sharif, 2025; Hayat et al., 2024).

The media is also considered one of the most important educational tools responsible for fostering political awareness among individuals, given its ability to reach large segments of society by providing them with political information, knowledge, and ideas. This is why governing regimes in all societies are keen to use the media and communication to disseminate the values and orientations of their ideology and the principles and ideas they espouse, through the content presented in various media outlets (Abu Rahma et al., 2025; Iraqi, 2013; Ghani et al., 2020).

As social media has brought about a radical shift in communication methods, leading to the emergence of new avenues for political engagement among college students, social media platforms have

become vibrant arenas where students launch movements—ranging from global movements such as #MeToo and Black Lives Matter to local protests around the world (Salam, et al., 2024; Batool, et al., 2020). Social media platforms such as Twitter, Facebook, YouTube, and others are not merely innovations in the online world; rather, their influence on public opinion is growing rapidly (Muzaffar, et al., 2019). With the growth of new communication technologies and the internet with its various applications, social media has become an important tool for individuals and institutions in acquiring political knowledge. There has been much discussion about its role in the political life of societies and its potential to bring about a qualitative shift in the fields of political media, awareness, education, and political change (Abdel Qader et al., 2024; Kholisoh et al., 2019; Siyal & Brohi, 2022). Despite the many benefits offered by new media, they also pose numerous risks; therefore, young people must maximize their benefits while avoiding these risks (Ezz El-Din, 2024; Fakeye, 2023).

Education plays a vital role in the development and progress of society and in instilling a sense of belonging and loyalty to the homeland. This is achieved through the contributions of educational institutions to the upbringing and development of individuals, as the political development of the educated individual is a fundamental goal of society. Education is one of the institutions capable of setting individuals on the right path, in line with the philosophy and development of society (Al-Ajmi, 2024; Choudhry et al., 2016). University education plays a crucial role in raising the level of political knowledge among university students and providing them with political education. University studies leave a clear imprint on their political culture, shaping their political behavior and their view of themselves and the political world around them. As a university student's political consciousness is shaped before they engage in politics (Abu Hamed, 2019).

Given the importance of the university years—both for the individual and for society—in fostering a sense of national belonging and strengthening political awareness, the university stage is considered the highest level of education an individual undergoes, providing a rich educational environment that encourages students to engage in political activities. It is the stage aimed at completing the development of a well-rounded national character—rational, emotional, and behavioral—and university students are at the beginning of their journey toward political participation, such as in general elections. Consequently, low political

awareness poses a serious threat to society, as it manifests in various negative behaviors such as the destruction of public property, the use of force and violence against state symbols and citizens, and a susceptibility to being recruited by terrorist and subversive groups (Al-Saied, 2019; Kuwoto et al., 2024).

Low political awareness also leads to a kind of political vacuum, apathy toward current events, narrow-mindedness, and a lack of proper understanding of national and global issues. This results in certain undesirable behaviors, as well as a lack of a sense of belonging, limited knowledge of individuals' political rights and duties, and an inability to grasp the broader picture of the reality surrounding them and understand the events and occurrences taking place around them (Jawamir & Sajit, 2024; Jones, 2023).

Therefore; Education is one of the pillars of building political awareness; therefore, its role must be activated to strengthen national unity by introducing reforms to the educational system and establishing a new educational philosophy whose core values are the state's protection of cultural identity and national unity, in accordance with a sound strategy aimed at building good, conscious citizens and committed to raising a new generation that loves its country and works to strengthen national identity, tolerance, and respect for all (Al-Fatlawi & Al-Ghatta, 2020).

The true challenge facing contemporary higher education lies in its ever-evolving role in serving society and driving change within it. People and communities look to their universities with high hopes that they will fulfill their intended role, as universities have come to play a vital part in raising public awareness and fostering cultural development, through the information and content they provide, which serves to elevate the cultural level and political awareness of university students. On the other hand, young people constitute an important segment of society, which requires them to be fully informed about current events and to possess political awareness and knowledge of what is happening so that they can take the lead in shaping public opinion in the future and contribute to the political sphere. University students must therefore possess at least a general understanding of politics to comprehend the reality around them and become active participants in decision-making. Ultimately, it is essential to examine the political awareness of university students (Saleh & Hussein, 2023). Some studies emphasize the need to link education with politics; if the two are separated, education may lose

its role in developing students' political awareness and shaping them politically, which may create a political gap among individuals, potentially leading to negative phenomena such as apathy and political alienation that could harm societal development. The separation of politics from education may be the primary cause of the spread of these phenomena (Khudair & Hassan, 2023). Accordingly, the research problem is defined by the following main question: What factors influence the formation of political awareness regarding participation in national general elections?

A series of sub-questions branch out from the main question, which can be clarified as follows:

1. What factors influence the formation of political awareness regarding participation in national general elections, particularly those related to societal circumstances having a political stamp?
2. What factors influence the formation of political awareness regarding participation in national general elections, particularly those related to the organizations of the civil society?
3. What factors influence the formation of political awareness regarding participation in national general elections and are related to the university?
4. What factors influence the formation of political awareness regarding participation in national general elections and are related to the family?
5. What factors influence the formation of political awareness regarding participation in national general elections and are related to the individual?

1.1. Objectives of the Study

The study aimed to identify the factors influencing the formation of political awareness regarding participation in national general elections, through:

1. Identifying the factors influencing the formation of political awareness regarding participation in national general elections that are linked to societal circumstances having a political stamp.
2. Identifying the factors influencing the formation of political awareness regarding participation in national general elections that are linked to the organizations of the civil society.
3. Identifying the factors influencing the formation of political awareness regarding

participation in national general elections that are linked to the university.

4. Identifying the factors influencing the formation of political awareness regarding participation in national general elections that are linked to the family.
5. To highlight the factors influencing the formation of political awareness regarding participation in national general elections and related to the individual.

1.2. Scientific Hypotheses

There is no statistically significant relationship at a significance level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the factors influencing the formation of political awareness and participation in national general elections attributable to the variables (gender, the academic year, the university, the place of residence, the average monthly household income and to the parents' educational level).

1.3. Significance of the Study

The significance of this study lies in obtaining new and reliable information about the factors influencing the formation of political awareness regarding participation in national general elections, and to draw conclusions that address the gaps in this field of knowledge, as well as to provide libraries and graduate students with a body of scholarly work on the factors influencing the formation of political awareness regarding participation in general national elections. This aims to raise their level of awareness, enhance their skills, and motivate them to conduct future studies on the subject to address the consequences of university students' reluctance to participate in.

1.4. Study Scope

Demographic Scope: The current study was conducted among undergraduate students at Al-Istiqal University, An-Najah National University, Hebron University and Palestine Technical University – Kadoorie in Palestine.

Geographical Scope: The current study was conducted at Al-Istiqal University, An-Najah National University, Hebron University and Palestine Technical University – Kadoorie in the West Bank, Palestine.

Temporal Scope: Data collection from the study participants took place during the period from December 2025 to March 2026.

1.5. Concepts of the Study

1.5.1. Political Awareness

Political awareness has been defined as a comprehensive understanding of political knowledge, values, and attitudes that enables an individual to recognize and analyze the conditions of their society and their stance toward them, and that motivates them to participate in order to change, develop, or preserve those conditions to achieve a better state of affairs (Al-Salili, 2018).

Political awareness is defined as a set of political values, attitudes, and principles that enable an individual to actively participate in analyzing the conditions and problems of their society, form judgments about them, determine their stance, and take action to improve and change them. Political awareness is based on political knowledge, forming a perception of political issues, and adopting and supporting a specific political stance, such as voting in elections and joining political organizations (Al-Shuwayhat, 2020; Mansour, 2023). Political awareness is the general understanding of the political climate and the dynamics and strategies of political actors within the country or even beyond its borders, given the global interconnectedness of events (Al-Laithi, 2021).

Political awareness is defined as the extent to which an individual understands their political reality, the conditions and realities of their society, region, and the world around them; the extent of their knowledge of what exists; their familiarity with possible and available political alternatives as frameworks for public life and solutions to the political problems facing society; and their understanding of the main prevailing and potential political concepts and terminology (Fritas, 2022; Al-Basrati, 2022). The concept of political awareness also refers to an individual's or citizen's knowledge of their political rights and duties, as well as the political events and developments taking place around them, and is formed through the individual's awareness of themselves and others around them (Al-Shalmani, 2025).

Political awareness has also been defined as the understanding among young people – or any other group – of the political and historical reality of their society, enabling young people to reach a stage of awareness regarding the political reality, their role in the political process, their participation in voting and electoral behavior, their political orientations, their affiliation with existing parties, and how to rely on all these variables to assess the political reality of their society and identify what should be supported or changed in this reality (Saadia, 2023). Political awareness is defined as the general understanding of

the political climate and the schemes and roles that dominate it; it encompasses the types of knowledge, values, and attitudes that constitute people’s political culture in terms of their relationship with political authority (Al-Jasser, 2020; Achour & Alghamdi, 2022).

The concept of political awareness is complex and consists of three components: political interest (the extent to which one is motivated to learn about politics), political knowledge (information regarding ideologies, political systems, and political processes), and political understanding (the ability to analyze and critically evaluate political events objectively) (Dauletova et al., 2022).

The researcher provides an operational definition of the concept of political awareness that is appropriate to the subject of the study, as follows: it refers to the knowledge, values, attitudes, and principles held by Palestinian university students that enable them to analyze and interpret political issues in Palestinian society, and motivate them to join political organizations and actively participate in national and local elections.

2. STUDY METHODOLOGY AND PROCEDURES:

2.1. Type Of Study

This study falls under the category of descriptive studies, as this type of research involves current facts regarding the nature of a phenomenon, situation, group of people, set of units, or set of conditions (Al-Dulaimi, 2016). Furthermore, descriptive research is a form of organized scientific analysis and interpretation aimed at describing a specific phenomenon or problem and quantifying it by collecting standardized data and information about the phenomenon or problem, classifying and analyzing it, and subjecting it to careful study (Abu Al-Nasr, 2017).

2.2. Research Methodology

The current study adopted a quantitative approach through a social survey, using a non-probability sample based on convenience sampling. A social survey involves describing and diagnosing a phenomenon, collecting data on it, and reporting on its current state—that is, what actually exists in a segment of society—through structured interviews

or questionnaires (Al-Mahmoudi, 2019). The aim is to obtain a set of data, interpret it, generalize it, and contextualize it, all for the purpose of scientific application (Daliou, 2023). Furthermore, a social survey is not merely a description or inventory of what actually exists; it goes beyond that to include other processes such as analysis, interpretation, and comparison of the current situation with other levels (Al-Fartousi & Al-Midani, 2023). Thus, it is well-suited to this study, both in terms of its subject matter and the adequacy of the data that can be collected.

2.3. Research Tool

The researcher used a questionnaire he had designed, after ensuring its validity and reliability. The questionnaire included seven items regarding the demographic data of the student respondents, The questionnaire also covered five themes comprising 69 statements related to factors influencing the formation of political awareness regarding participation in national general elections: A field study was conducted on a sample of undergraduate students at Al-Istiklal University, An-Najah National University, Hebron University, and Palestine Technical University. Thus, the total number of questionnaire items was 76. The questionnaire used Likert’s five-point scale as follows: Strongly agree (5), Agree (4), Neutral (3), Disagree (2), Strongly disagree (1).

1. Validation of the instrument: The researcher ensured the validity of the instrument by presenting it to a number of experienced and specialized reviewers in Palestine (the West Bank and the Gaza Strip) as well as other Arab countries. Experts and faculty members exchanged ideas and analyses regarding the reformulation of certain study statements to ensure that all dimensions of the subject under study were covered. Some adjustments were made to the wording of the statements, and after the required adjustments were made, the reviewers confirmed the validity of the study tool.
2. Instrument reliability: The researcher verified the reliability of the instrument using Cronbach’s alpha, and the reliability coefficients for the instrument’s subscales were as follows:

Table (1): Study Reliability Coefficients Using Cronbach’s Alpha

Cronbach's alpha coefficient	Number of paragraphs	Themes	N
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0.822	17	Theme 1 : Factors influencing the formation of political awareness regarding participation in national general elections, as related the societal circumstances having a political stamp	1
0.858	12	Theme 2: Factors influencing the formation of political awareness regarding participation in national general elections and related to the organizations of the civil society	2
0.916	15	Theme 3: Factors influencing the formation of political awareness regarding participation in national general elections and those related to the university	3
0.893	11	Theme 4: Factors influencing the formation of political awareness regarding participation in national general elections and those related to the family	4
0.850	14	Theme 5: Factors influencing the formation of political awareness regarding participation in national general elections and related to the individual	5
0.947	69	Overall Grade	

Table 1 shows that the study's dimensions have high reliability coefficients; the overall reliability coefficient was 0.947, which is a high value, and these results are sufficient for the purposes of the current study.

2.4. Sample, Data Collection Procedures, And Ethical Approvals

2.4.1. Sample And Selection Procedures

The researcher conducted this study and applied it to a non-probability sample using the available methodology; the study sample consisted of 412 undergraduate students from in Al-Istiqlal University, An-Najah National University, Hebron University and Palestine Technical University - Kadoorie, Given the exceptional circumstances of the genocide campaign against the Palestinian people by

the Zionist occupation and the 2026 Zionist-Iranian war, the electronic questionnaire was distributed and circulated through the academic affairs offices at the aforementioned Palestinian universities, as well as through their deans of graduate studies and scientific research and deans of student affairs. The study relied on clear inclusion criteria: (1) The participant must be Palestinian and a student during the 2025–2026 academic year, (2) The participant must voluntarily agree to participate. Due to field and communication constraints associated with the occupation and difficult economic conditions, which prevented reaching all students, participation was limited to students who had access to the online survey and were able to complete it.

Table (2) shows the distribution of the study sample according to its variables as follows:

Table (2): Presents A Description of the Study Sample and Its Demographic Characteristics According to the Variables.

Percentage (%)	Repetition	Variable levels	The variable
51.7	213	Male	Gender
48.3	199	female	
100.0	412	Total	
25.5	105	First	Academic Year
12.6	52	Second	
24.8	102	Third	
23.5	97	Fourth	
13.6	56	Fifth	
100.0	412	Total	
21.1	87	Al-Istiqlal Uni.	University
41.3	170	An-Najah Nat. Uni.	
18.0	74	Hebron Uni.	
19.7	81	Palestine Tec. Uni.	
100.0	412	Total	
41.7	172	City	Place of residence
50.2	207	Village	
8.0	33	Camp	
100.0	412	Total	
48.5	200	Less than 2,000 shekels	Average monthly household income

19.4	80	From 2,000 to less than 4,000 shekels	
17.5	72	From 4,000 to less than 6,000 shekels	
14.6	60	6,000 shekels and above	
100.0	412	Total	
38.6	159	High school or lower.	Parents' educational level
44.9	185	Bachelor's degree.	
16.5	68	Graduate studies.	
100.0	412	Total	

2.5. Procedures And Ethical Considerations

The researcher adhered to internationally recognized general principles of research ethics, such as respect for human dignity, informed consent, confidentiality and privacy, non-maleficence, beneficence, justice, transparency, and accountability, Given the exceptional circumstances facing Palestinian society during the genocide.

The researcher followed the following procedures:

1. Informed consent: The online survey included an introductory page explaining the research objectives and nature of the study, as well as participants' rights, while emphasizing that participation was entirely voluntary and that participants had the right to withdraw at any time without any obligation.
2. Confidentiality and Privacy: No direct identifying information was collected, and all responses were stored in secure electronic files accessible only to the researcher, with the data used strictly for scientific purposes in accordance with research principles.
3. Non-harm: The questionnaire was designed with the psychological and social well-being of participants in mind, avoiding questions that might cause trauma or additional stress to the students being studied.
4. Purpose: The study aims to document the factors influencing the formation of political awareness regarding participation in national general elections, thereby contributing to the Palestinian community and decision-makers.
5. Responsibility and Fairness: The researcher made every effort to distribute the research tool (the online survey link) fairly among students at the aforementioned universities, while ensuring that participation did not place an additional burden on the responding students given the difficult circumstances caused by the ongoing war of genocide.

Although the researcher obtained official approval to distribute the link to the online survey to students at the aforementioned Palestinian universities, and despite the fact that the

administrations of Birzeit University and the Arab American University declined to circulate the survey link for unclear reasons, the researcher adhered to these general principles to ensure that the study was conducted according to the highest possible ethical standards under wartime conditions.

The constraints that determined the sample size:

The fact that the sample size was limited to 412 participants was not so much a research choice as it was a direct result of a series of practical constraints linked to the circumstances of the genocide being perpetrated against the Palestinian people and the 2026 Zionist-Iranian war.

The researcher faced several factors that limited access to a larger number of students, most notably:

1. Security restrictions: The ongoing siege and the fragmentation of Palestinian cities have prevented field surveys from being conducted or direct access to all students.
2. Psychological and social pressures: The state of fear, anxiety, and uncertainty experienced by Palestinian students due to the genocide campaign and the 2026 Zionist-Iranian war has reduced their willingness to participate in academic studies or devote time to answering questionnaires.
3. Instrument-induced selectivity: The reliance on an online questionnaire automatically excluded a segment of students who do not own smartphones or have internet access, which reduced the response rate.
4. Economic circumstances: Some students were forced to sell their personal belongings and smartphones to use the proceeds to provide food and drink for their families or to pay university tuition and cover transportation costs, especially in light of the Zionist financial blockade imposed on the Palestinian people.
5. Timing: The data collection period coincided with a critical phase of the war and the blockade, causing a number of students to decline participation due to their preoccupation with securing their basic needs.
6. Living conditions: Students are constantly preoccupied with meeting their daily needs

throughout the day and stand in long lines for hours at the Zionist checkpoints that cut off Palestinian cities.

7. Medical and emergency circumstances: There is scarcely a Palestinian family that has not experienced the martyrdom or injury (whether serious, moderate, or minor) of a family member, or the imprisonment of innocent family members in Israeli prisons as a result of the campaign of genocide. This situation negatively affects students' willingness to cooperate with the researcher in completing the online questionnaire.

Consequently, the limited sample size reflects overwhelming field challenges rather than shortcomings in the research design, which necessitates interpreting the results with caution and viewing them as a reflection of exceptional circumstances that do not permit standard procedures for expanding the sample size or ensuring full representation of all groups. Conducting this study under unprecedented circumstances – namely, a campaign of genocide and the 2026 Zionist-Iranian war – which affected people, trees, and stones, presents a challenge that is difficult for researchers in various scientific and academic fields worldwide to address.

2.6. Statistical Analyses:

After collecting the responses from the study sample, the data were coded and entered into a computer, then statistically analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). The statistical analyses used included: frequencies, arithmetic means, percentages, standard deviations, the independent t-test, and one-way ANOVA, as well as Cronbach's alpha to calculate the reliability coefficient. To interpret the study results, the researcher used the following arithmetic mean categories: less than 1.80 – very low; 1.81–2.60 – low; 2.61–3.40 – moderate; 3.41–4.20 – high; and 4.21–5.00 – very high.

2.7. Presentation of the Field Study Results and Recommendations

In the preceding pages, the researcher has presented the theoretical and methodological aspects of the study. Here, the researcher presents the results of the field study. The following are the results of the study, organized according to the sequence of the research questions:

If a general national election were held, would you participate?

Table (3): Responses from the Study Sample Regarding Participation in National Elections (N = 412).

Ranking	percentage	Repetition	Variable level	Variables
1	68.7	283	Yes	Voting in the elections
2	31.3	129	No	
			Total	

Table 3 shows that a high percentage of the study sample 68.7% expressed a willingness to participate in national elections if they were held, compared to 31.3% who stated they did not intend to participate. These results reflect a general positive inclination among the majority of the sample toward engaging in the electoral process, which can be explained by an acceptable level of political awareness or a sense of the importance of participation in influencing the course of political life.

Conversely, the significant proportion (nearly one-third) of respondents who do not intend to participate is an important indicator that cannot be ignored, as it may reflect a lack of trust in the electoral process, a sense of its futility, or frustration with the

current political reality. This result may also be linked to various factors such as the political climate, past experiences, or a lack of conviction that elections can bring about real change.

Based on this, it can be said that there is a popular base supporting participation; however, there is still a need to build trust and motivate hesitant or resistant groups by improving the political environment, increasing transparency, and enhancing the credibility of the electoral process.

The answer to the first question, which reads: What factors influence the formation of political awareness regarding participation in national general elections, particularly those related to societal circumstances having a political stamp?

Table (4): Factors Influence the Formation of Political Awareness Regarding Participation in National General Elections; Particularly Those Related to Societal Circumstances Having a Political Stamp.

Appreciation	percentage	Standard dev.	Mean	Paragraphs	Number	Ranking
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High	80.4	.94	4.02	The scenes of war and its repercussions contributed to raising my political awareness and increased my following of political analyses and public discussions.	12	1
High	78.6	.84	3.93	The Zionist occupation's restrictions on elections in Jerusalem negatively affect the political awareness of young people.	2	2
High	78.2	.80	3.91	The recent Gaza war contributed to deepening my awareness of the nature of the Palestinian political system and the limits of its effectiveness in managing the conflict with the occupation.	8	3
High	77.6	.92	3.88	I believe that the political division between the Palestinian forces will continue regardless of the outcome of the elections.	7	4
High	76.8	.94	3.84	The Gaza war reshaped my political priorities, putting national issues ahead of individual and service concerns.	11	5
High	76.0	.90	3.80	The Gaza war deepened my awareness of the relationship between weak political representation and continuing national crises.	16	6
High	75.4	.96	3.77	The repercussions of the Gaza war revealed a clear gap between Palestinian political discourse and field reality, which affected my level of confidence in the electoral process.	9	7
High	74.6	.90	3.73	The Gaza war has contributed to a more mature political attitude toward electoral participation as a political act rather than a formality.	17	8
High	74.4	1.00	3.72	The Gaza war highlighted the importance of popular legitimacy and elected institutions in confronting external pressures and security challenges.	14	9
High	74.2	.98	3.71	The Gaza war has strengthened my conviction that political and electoral participation represents one of the tools of political resilience, despite its limited direct results.	10	10
High	73.0	1.04	3.65	The Gaza war has weakened my belief in the ability of elections alone to bring about fundamental change in light of the continuing Palestinian political division.	13	11
High	71.6	1.02	3.58	Israeli barriers between cities limit my ability to participate in elections.	3	12
High	71.6	.95	3.58	The repercussions of the Gaza war prompted me to reevaluate the feasibility of participating in elections in the absence of a comprehensive national political consensus.	15	13

High	71.2	1.00	3.56	My confidence in political organizations declined after the division in the Palestinian political system in 2007.	1	14
High	70.0	1.13	3.50	The repeated settler attacks make me feel that participating in the elections will not change the security situation.	6	15
High	69.8	1.18	3.49	Fear of political arrest weakens my ability to participate in elections.	4	16
Average	67.0	1.19	3.35	The fear of being arrested by the occupation authorities contributes to limiting my participation in the elections.	5	17
High	74.2	0.50	3.71	The overall score of the axis		

Table 4 shows that the items related to factors influencing the formation of political awareness regarding participation in national general elections—and linked to political societal conditions—scored highly, with arithmetic means ranging from 3.35 to 4.02. The item with the highest arithmetic mean was item No. (12), which reads: “The scenes of war and its repercussions contributed to raising my political awareness and increased my following of political analyses and public discussions” with an arithmetic mean of (4.02) and a percentage of (80.4%). and the statement with the lowest arithmetic mean was statement No. (5), which reads: “The fear of being arrested by the occupation authorities contributes to limiting my participation in the elections” with an arithmetic mean of (3.35) and a percentage of (67%), Consequently, this result indicates that the factors influencing the formation of political awareness regarding participation in general national elections and linked to political societal conditions were high, as evidenced by the overall score, which had an arithmetic mean of (3.71) and a percentage of (74.2%).

The researcher attributes this finding to the nature of the political and social environment in which members of society live, which is characterized by the intensity and rapid pace of events. This contributes to raising their level of political awareness, especially given the constant presence of national issues in daily life imposed by wars and their repercussions. The effects of these

circumstances are not limited to daily life alone, but extend to foster a state of intellectual and political engagement, prompting individuals to follow public analyses and discussions more closely. The researcher also notes that continuous interaction with the media—both traditional and modern—has contributed to strengthening this awareness by providing a broad space for the circulation of information and the interpretation of events, which has helped foster more mature political perceptions among individuals regarding participation in national elections. Regarding the relative decline in the influence of the fear of arrest, the researcher explains this within the framework of societal adaptation to political and security pressures, as this factor no longer constitutes a decisive obstacle to the formation of political awareness or interest in public affairs, compared to the influence of other factors of a collective and national nature. Accordingly, the researcher asserts that the rise in the overall arithmetic mean reflects a high level of political awareness linked to political societal conditions, which is directly related to the specific nature of the political context currently facing Palestinian society and contributes to fostering interest in participating in general national elections.

The answer to the second question, which reads: What factors influence the formation of political awareness regarding participation in national general elections, particularly those related to the organizations of the civil society?

Table (5): Factors Influence the Formation of Political Awareness Regarding Participation in National General Elections; Particularly Those Related to the Organizations of the Civil Society.

Appreciation	percentage	Standard dev.	Mean	Paragraphs	Number	Ranking
High	80.2	.9	4.01	The Gaza war worked to strengthen the Palestinian national narrative locally and globally.	11	1
High	79.4	.86	3.97	Lack of interest in political organization committees to provide clear programs on the needs and problems of youth.	3	2

High	79.4	.85	3.97	Lack of interest from government media institutions and newspapers in spreading the values of democracy and participation among young people.	4	3
High	79.0	.77	3.95	Lack of interest of political organization committees in exchanging political ideas among young people.	10	4
High	77.6	.80	3.88	The Gaza war activated the media role of the committees of Palestinian political organizations.	12	5
High	77.2	.92	3.86	Newspaper and magazine platforms are not committed to presenting young people's opinions and suggestions.	5	6
High	77.2	.81	3.86	The failure of political organization committees to express the civility of society and its escalating needs.	8	7
High	76.8	.92	3.84	Palestinian youth and sports centers' interest in youth political activities has declined.	7	8
High	75.6	.82	3.78	The interest of Palestinian political organizations' committees in the issue of political culture has declined.	1	9
High	75.2	.78	3.76	Civil society organizations fear the issue of political culture.	2	10
High	75.0	.93	3.75	Low interest in youth political culture among professional unions, civil society organizations, and labor federations.	6	11
High	70.4	1.00	3.52	Some political organizing committees focus on religious culture rather than political culture.	9	12
High	77.0	0.54	3.85	The overall score of the axis		

Table 5 shows that the items regarding factors influencing the formation of political awareness toward participation in national general elections and linked to civil society organizations scored high, with arithmetic means ranging from 3.52 to 4.01. The item with the highest arithmetic mean was item No. (11), which states, "The Gaza war worked to strengthen the Palestinian national narrative locally and globally" with an arithmetic mean of (4.01) and a percentage of (80.2%). The statement with the lowest arithmetic mean was statement No. (9), which reads: "Some political organizing committees focus on religious culture rather than political culture" with an arithmetic mean of (3.52) and a percentage of (70.4%). Consequently, this result indicates that the factors influencing the formation of political awareness regarding participation in general national elections and linked to civil society organizations were high, as evidenced by the overall score, which had an arithmetic mean of (3.85) and a percentage of (77%).

The researcher attributes this finding to the growing role played by civil society organizations in shaping political awareness, particularly given the

complex political conditions facing Palestinian society. Through their activities and awareness-raising programs, these organizations have contributed to enhancing individuals' awareness of national issues and reinforcing the concept of political participation as a fundamental tool for influencing public discourse. The researcher also notes that the escalation of major events, foremost among them the Gaza War, has afforded civil society organizations greater space to highlight the Palestinian national narrative at both the local and international levels. This has positively impacted individuals' level of political awareness and strengthened their interest in following and engaging with public affairs. This interaction between political events and the performance of these organizations has contributed to raising awareness regarding participation in elections. Conversely, the researcher explains the lower average score for the section regarding some organizations' committees focusing on religious culture rather than political culture by noting that this orientation may relatively limit the effectiveness of political awareness-raising discourse; however, it did not have a decisive impact

in light of other, more influential factors related to the national dimension and general political conditions. Accordingly, the researcher asserts that the notable increase in the arithmetic means reflects the effectiveness of civil society organizations in fostering advanced political awareness, driven by their engagement with the national context and their

ability to direct public attention toward the importance of participating in general national elections.

The answer to the third question, which reads: What factors influence the formation of political awareness regarding participation in national general elections and are related to the university?

Table (6): Factors Influence the Formation of Political Awareness Regarding Participation in National General Elections and Are Related to the University.

Appreciation	percentage	Standard dev.	Mean	Paragraphs	Number	Ranking
High	80.0	.81	4.00	Poor development of citizenship values among students contributes to their low participation in political life.	3	1
High	78.2	.94	3.91	The university administration fears the occupation authorities' actions towards the university.	12	2
High	76.4	.98	3.82	The university administration's concern for the educational process.	11	3
High	76.2	.93	3.81	Weak political dialogue between students within the university halls.	4	4
High	75.2	1.06	3.76	Some professors ignored students' discussion of political issues within the university.	2	5
High	75.0	.96	3.75	The university's interest in spreading political culture among students has declined.	1	6
High	75.0	.99	3.75	The role of student blocs at the university in developing students' political awareness has declined.	13	7
High	74.8	.99	3.74	The university's interest is limited to students' cultural activities.	7	8
High	74.8	.99	3.74	The university's separation from the political issues of young people.	9	9
High	74.2	1.06	3.71	The university administration's lack of interest in student participation in the political process.	6	10
High	74.0	1.07	3.70	The university imposes restrictions on political activities on campus.	8	11
High	74.0	1.01	3.70	The low efficiency of university courses in promoting political culture among students.	15	12
High	69.8	1.07	3.49	The Student Council encourages constructive political dialogue among students at the university.	14	13
High	69.4	1.07	3.47	The decline in political activities on campus affects the educational process.	5	14
Average	65.8	1.02	3.29	University professors' lack of political culture.	10	15
High	74.2	.68	3.71	The overall score of the axis		

Table 6 shows that the items related to factors influencing the formation of political awareness regarding participation in national general elections and linked to the university scored high, with arithmetic means ranging from 3.29 to 4.00. The item with the highest arithmetic mean was Item 3, which states, "Poor development of citizenship values among students contributes to their low participation in political life" with an arithmetic mean of 4.00 and a percentage of 80%. The statement with the lowest

arithmetic mean was statement No. (10), which reads: "University professors' lack of political culture" with an arithmetic mean of (3.29) and a percentage of (65.8%). Consequently, this result indicates that the factors influencing the formation of political awareness regarding participation in national general elections and those related to the university were high, as indicated by the overall score, which had an arithmetic mean of (3.71) and a percentage of (74.2%).

The researcher attributes this finding to the pivotal role that the university plays, as an educational and social institution, in shaping students' awareness – not only on an academic level, but also on a political and civic level. The university represents an interactive environment that allows students to engage with diverse ideas and participate in public debates, which contributes to developing their awareness of national issues and the importance of participating in political life. The researcher believes that the fact that the item regarding the weak development of civic values received the highest mean score reflects students' high awareness of the importance of these values in enhancing their political participation, as a sense of belonging and national responsibility constitutes a fundamental motivation for engaging in elections. This indicates that students possess a critical awareness of the shortcomings in the university environment regarding the promotion of these values. Conversely,

the researcher explains the low average score for the item regarding university professors' lack of political culture by noting that students do not view this factor as a major obstacle. This may be attributed to the diversity of their sources of political knowledge, which are not limited to faculty members, given their exposure to the media and social media platforms. Accordingly, the researcher asserts that the high overall score reflects the contribution of the university environment – including its academic and social interactions – to the formation of a notable political awareness among students, although this is influenced to varying degrees by the extent to which civic values are established and reinforced on campus.

The answer to the fourth question, which reads: What factors influence the formation of political awareness regarding participation in national general elections and are related to the family?

Table (7): Factors Influence the Formation of Political Awareness Regarding Participation in National General Elections and Are Related to the Family.

Appreciation	percentage	Standard dev.	Mean	Paragraphs	Number	Ranking
High	81.0	1.00	4.05	The family's fear of the Israeli occupation for the future of its children.	10	1
High	76.0	1.10	3.80	Family concern for economic needs at the expense of political culture.	11	2
Average	70.4	1.12	3.52	Weak family encouragement of youth involvement in political organizations.	7	3
High	68.8	1.05	3.44	Low level of family dialogue with young people on important political matters.	5	4
Average	65.2	1.07	3.26	Weak family interest in the political upbringing of young people.	4	5
Average	63.4	1.24	3.17	The lack of democratic values related to accepting other opinions within the family.	8	6
Average	62.8	1.13	3.14	Family members do not participate in parliamentary elections.	6	7
Average	61.6	1.23	3.08	The family's lack of respect for its children's intellectual privacy.	9	8
Average	60.8	1.16	3.04	The family's disregard for important political issues.	3	9
Average	60.4	1.19	3.02	There is a weakness in the political culture of my family members.	2	10
Average	59.6	1.19	2.98	My family ignores my political views and orientations.	1	11
Average	66.4	0.79	3.32	The overall score of the axis		

Table 7 shows that the items related to family-related factors influencing political awareness regarding participation in national general elections received moderate scores, with arithmetic means ranging from 2.98 to 4.05. The item with the highest arithmetic mean was item (10), which reads "The family's fear of the Israeli occupation for the future of

its children." with an arithmetic mean of (4.05) and a percentage of (81%). The item with the lowest arithmetic mean was item No. (1), which reads "My family ignores my political views and orientations" with an arithmetic mean of (2.98) and a percentage of (59.6%). Consequently, this result indicates that the factors influencing the formation of political

awareness regarding participation in national general elections and related to the family were moderate, as indicated by the overall score, which had an arithmetic mean of (3.32) and a percentage of (66.4%).

The researcher attributes this finding to the complex nature of the family's role in shaping political awareness, as it exerts an indirect influence in which emotional and social dimensions intertwine with the political dimension; As the primary nurturing environment for the individual, the family contributes to the transmission of values and general attitudes; however, its influence in the political sphere is often characterized by caution, particularly in environments facing complex security and political conditions. The researcher explains the high average score for the item regarding families' fear for their children's future in light of the political and security context, as families tend to adopt conservative stances aimed at protecting their children from potential risks. This reflects the presence of the security factor as one of the main

determinants in shaping political attitudes within the family. While this fear serves as a motive for caution, it also contributes to raising children's awareness of the nature of the political reality and its complexities. Conversely, the low average score regarding the family's disregard for children's political views indicates a degree of dialogue and interaction within the family, allowing for the exchange of viewpoints and the inclusion of differing opinions. This reinforces the individual's autonomy in forming their political consciousness. Consequently, the researcher believes that the "moderate" nature of the family's influence stems from a balance between its role in social and political socialization on the one hand, and its desire to avoid exposing its children to risks on the other, which makes its influence present but less intense compared to some other institutions and circumstances.

The answer to the fifth question, which reads: What factors influence the formation of political awareness regarding participation in national general elections and are related to the individual?

Table (8): Factors Influence the Formation of Political Awareness Regarding Participation in National General Elections and Are Related to the Individual.

Appreciation	percentage	Standard dev.	Mean	Paragraphs	Number	Ranking
High	83.4	.82	4.17	Economic problems of youth.	2	1
High	82.2	.87	4.11	Young people are increasingly busy with social media.	12	2
High	81.8	.88	4.09	The use of technology has affected youth culture.	13	3
High	81.6	.93	4.08	Low confidence of youth in Palestinian organizations.	14	4
High	80.2	.84	4.01	Social problems of youth.	3	5
High	79.8	.95	3.99	Young people lose confidence in the election results.	5	6
High	79.0	.90	3.95	Poor cultural level of youth.	1	7
High	78.8	.94	3.94	Youth attendance at political seminars has declined.	9	8
High	78.4	.99	3.92	Psychological frustration of young people due to the negative performance of the Palestinian political system.	7	9
High	78.0	.93	3.90	Young people's loss of confidence in the Palestinian political system.	6	10
High	75.6	.86	3.78	Weak youth participation in the electoral process.	10	11
High	73.2	1.06	3.66	Low youth follow-up on important political issues.	8	12
High	71.2	1.22	3.56	I feel that my electoral vote is influential in the election process.	11	13
High	70.8	1.08	3.54	The weak value of youth's belonging to the homeland.	4	14
High	78.2	0.55	3.91	The overall score of the axis		

Table 8 shows that the items related to individual-level factors influencing political awareness regarding participation in national general elections received high scores, with arithmetic means ranging

from 3.54 to 4.17. The item with the highest arithmetic mean was Item No. (2), which reads "Economic problems of youth" with an arithmetic mean of (4.17) and a percentage of (83.4%), The item

with the lowest arithmetic mean was item No. (4), which read “The weak value of youth's belonging to the homeland” with an arithmetic mean of (3.54) and a percentage of (70.8%). Consequently, this result indicates that the factors influencing the formation of political awareness regarding participation in national general elections and related to the individual were high, as indicated by the overall score, which had an arithmetic mean of (3.91) and a percentage of (78.2%).

The researcher attributes this finding to the growing role of individual factors in shaping political awareness, particularly in light of the economic and social transformations that directly affect young people’s lives. Economic pressures, chief among them unemployment and the rising cost of living, serve as a catalyst for increasing young people’s interest in politics, as a sphere through which they can influence public policies related to their living conditions and future. The researcher believes that the fact that the section on economic issues received the highest average score reflects a deep awareness among young people of the link between their economic conditions and political decisions, which drives them to develop a more mature political consciousness based on the connection between government performance and their daily lives. This

reinforces their tendency to follow public issues and engage in discussions related to elections. Conversely, the researcher explains the low average score for the section on weak national belonging by noting that a sense of belonging remains present among young people to a reasonable degree and has not reached a level that constitutes a fundamental obstacle to the formation of political awareness or participation, despite the challenges they face. Based on this, the researcher asserts that the high overall score reflects that the individual, through their daily experiences and observations, has become a central factor in the development of political awareness, where economic factors intersect with political awareness to drive greater interest in participating in general national elections.

3. RESULTS OF THE SCIENTIFIC HYPOTHESES

Results of the first hypothesis, which states: There is no statistically significant relationship at a significance level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the factors influencing the formation of political awareness and participation in national general elections attributable to the gender variable.

To test this hypothesis, an independent samples t-test was used, as shown in Table 9.

Table (9): Results of the T-Test for Two Independent Groups to Examine the Significance of Differences in the Responses of Study Participants Regarding the Factors Influencing the Formation of Political Awareness Toward Participation in National General Elections, according to the Gender Variable.

Level of significance	T-value	Degrees of freedom	Standard dev.	Mean	Number	Gender	Topic
.262	1.122	410	.52344	3.7379	213	Male	Factors related to societal circumstances having a political stamp
			.48651	3.6819	199	Female	
.002	3.175	410	.53964	3.9347	213	Male	Factors related to the organizations of the civil society
			.54693	3.7647	199	Female	
.368	.901	410	.75003	3.7433	213	Male	Factors related to the university
			.60072	3.6827	199	Female	
.179	1.346	410	.79598	3.3747	213	Male	Factors related to the family
			.78938	3.2695	199	Female	
.155	1.425	410	.57171	3.9507	213	Male	Factors related to the individual
			.54420	3.8722	199	Female	

Table (9) shows that the significance level is higher than required in the study ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the responses of the study sample regarding the factors influencing the formation of political awareness toward participation in national general elections, attributed to the gender variable across all dimensions, while differences were found in the factors related to civil society organizations, and these differences favored males.

The researcher attributes this finding to the convergence of experiences and the social and

political conditions faced by both men and women, as both groups are exposed to the same general context of events and challenges. This contributes to the formation of a political awareness that is largely similar, explaining the absence of statistically significant differences across most dimensions. The researcher also believes that exposure to the media and social media platforms, along with easy access to political information, has helped narrow the gender gap in political awareness, such that this awareness is no longer the exclusive domain of one group over

another, but rather the product of a shared societal experience. Regarding the emergence of differences on the civil society organizations axis in favor of males, the researcher attributes this to the nature of field participation, as males may have greater opportunities for direct engagement in the activities of these organizations – whether for social or cultural reasons or due to the nature of the movement and public work – which grants them broader experience in this field. This is reflected in their level of awareness specifically related to this area. Based on this, the researcher asserts that the gender variable was not a decisive factor in shaping political

awareness in general, with the exception of what relates to the degree of practical engagement in civil society institutions, which may vary depending on the opportunities available to both men and women. **The results of the second hypothesis, which states: There is no statistically significant relationship at a significance level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the factors influencing the formation of political awareness and participation in national general elections attributable to the academic year variable.**

To test this hypothesis, I used a one-way ANOVA, as shown in Table 10.

Table (10): Results of the One-Way ANOVA For the Study Sample's Responses Regarding the Factors Influencing the Formation of Political Awareness Toward Participation in National General Elections, according to the Academic Year Variable.

Level of significance	F-value	Mean of the squares	Degrees of freedom	Total squares	Source of the discrepancy	Variables
.177	1.585	.404	4	1.614	Between groups	Factors related to societal circumstances having a political stamp
		.255	407	103.659	Within groups	
			411	105.273	Total	
.115	1.868	.559	4	2.234	Between groups	Factors related to the organizations of the civil society
		.299	407	121.704	Within groups	
			411	123.938	Total	
.063	2.247	1.032	4	4.129	Between groups	Factors related to the university
		.459	407	186.958	Within groups	
			411	191.087	Total	
.054	2.351	1.462	4	5.846	Between groups	Factors related to the family
		.622	407	252.991	Within groups	
			411	258.838	Total	
.200	1.506	.469	4	1.875	Between groups	Factors related to the individual
		.311	407	126.691	Within groups	
			411	128.566	Total	

Table (10) shows that the significance level is higher than that required in the study ($\alpha \leq 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted, indicating that there are no statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the responses of the study sample regarding the factors influencing the formation of political awareness toward participation in national general elections, as attributed to the academic year variable.

The researcher attributes this finding to the fact that students, regardless of their year of study, are exposed to a university environment that is similar in terms of educational content and social experiences, which limits the existence of significant differences in their level of political awareness. As a unified institutional framework, the university provides students with similar opportunities to learn about and engage with political issues, whether through coursework or extracurricular activities. The researcher also argues that the greatest influence on the formation of political awareness is not linked to the academic year as much as it is to factors outside

the academic framework, such as the general political reality, the media, and social media platforms – factors to which all students are exposed to a similar degree regardless of their academic level. Furthermore, the nature of the national issues at hand – and they're inherently pressing and urgent character – contributes to the development of early political awareness among students from their earliest years, thereby reducing the likelihood of clear cumulative differences emerging as they progress through their academic years. Based on this, the researcher asserts that the absence of differences reflects a homogeneity in the sources shaping students' political awareness, and that the academic year did not constitute a significant variable in this context compared to other factors that are more prominent and influential.

The results of the third hypothesis, which states: There is no statistically significant relationship at a significance level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the factors influencing the formation of political awareness and participation in national general elections

attributable to the university variable.

as shown in Table 11.

To test this hypothesis, I used a one-way ANOVA,

Table (11): Results of the One-Way ANOVA For the Study Sample's Responses Regarding the Factors Influencing the Formation of Political Awareness Toward Participation in National General Elections, according to the University Variable.

Level of significance	F-value	Mean of the squares	Degrees of freedom	Total squares	Source of the discrepancy	Variables
.804	.330	.085	3	.255	Between groups	Factors related to societal circumstances having a political stamp
		.257	408	105.019	Within groups	
			411	105.273	Total	
.967	.088	.027	3	.080	Between groups	Factors related to the organizations of the civil society
		.304	408	123.858	Within groups	
			411	123.938	Total	
.066	2.415	1.111	3	3.334	Between groups	Factors related to the university
		.460	408	187.753	Within groups	
			411	191.087	Total	
.169	1.686	1.057	3	3.170	Between groups	Factors related to the family
		.627	408	255.667	Within groups	
			411	258.838	Total	
.631	.576	.181	3	.542	Between groups	Factors related to the individual
		.314	408	128.024	Within groups	
			411	128.566	Total	

Table (11) shows that the significance level is higher than that required in the study ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted, stating that there are no statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the responses of the study sample regarding the factors influencing the formation of political awareness toward participation in general national elections, attributable to the university variable.

The researcher attributes this finding to the fact that universities, despite their differences, operate within a similar educational and cultural environment in terms of curricula and extracurricular activities, which contributes to shaping a similar level of political awareness among students. Furthermore, the influence of the media and social media—which have become the primary sources of political information—extends beyond the university campus and creates a state of homogeneity in students' attitudes toward national issues,

including participation in elections. Additionally, the absence of differences may stem from the similarity of the social, economic, and political conditions in which students live, which play a pivotal role in shaping their political awareness to a greater extent than the influence of the university itself. Consequently, the university is no longer the decisive factor in shaping political awareness; rather, it is part of a broader system of overlapping influences that contribute to directing individuals' attitudes toward political participation.

The results of the fourth hypothesis, which states: There is no statistically significant relationship at a significance level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the factors influencing the formation of political awareness and participation in national general elections attributable to the variable of place of residence.

To test this hypothesis, I used a one-way ANOVA, as shown in Table 12.

Table (12): Results of the One-Way ANOVA For the Study Sample's Responses Regarding the Factors Influencing the Formation of Political Awareness Toward Participation in National General Elections, according to the Variable of Place of Residence.

Level of significance	F-value	Mean of the squares	Degrees of freedom	Total squares	Source of the discrepancy	Variables
.524	.647	.166	2	.332	Between groups	Factors related to societal circumstances having a political stamp
		.257	409	104.941	Within groups	
			411	105.273	Total	
.886	.121	.037	2	.073	Between groups	Factors related to the organizations of the civil society
		.303	409	123.865	Within groups	
			411	123.938	Total	
.481	.734	.342	2	.684	Between groups	Factors related to the university
		.466	409	190.404	Within groups	
			411	191.087	Total	

.159	1.848	1.159	2	2.318	Between groups	Factors related to the family
		.627	409	256.520	Within groups	
			411	258.838	Total	
.961	.040	.012	2	.025	Between groups	Factors related to the individual
		.314	409	128.541	Within groups	
			411	128.566	Total	

Table (12) shows that the significance level is higher than that required in the study ($\alpha \leq 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted, indicating that there are no statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the responses of the study sample regarding the factors influencing the formation of political awareness toward participation in general national elections, attributable to the variable of place of residence.

The researcher attributes this finding to the fact that the influence of place of residence is no longer a decisive factor in shaping individuals' political awareness, given the current state of information accessibility and the significant advancements in communication technologies. The proliferation of traditional and digital media, alongside social media, has helped narrow the gaps between different residential environments—whether urban, rural, or in camps—and created a convergence in the level of knowledge and interest in political issues. This result can also be explained by the fact that individuals, regardless of where they live, are exposed to largely

similar political and social conditions, particularly in the broader national context, which reinforces their unified tendencies toward participating in elections. In addition, educational institutions and organizational and party frameworks play a role in creating a convergent political awareness that transcends the geographical boundaries of place of residence. Consequently, place of residence no longer represents a fundamentally influential variable in shaping political awareness, but rather has become part of a broader system of interrelated factors that contribute to guiding individuals' behavior and attitudes toward electoral participation.

The results of the fifth hypothesis, which states: There is no statistically significant relationship at a significance level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the factors influencing the formation of political awareness and participation in national general elections and the variable of average monthly household income.

To test this hypothesis, I used a one-way ANOVA, as shown in Table 13.

Table (13): Results of the One-Way ANOVA For the Study Sample's Responses Regarding the Factors Influencing the Formation of Political Awareness Toward Participation in National General Elections, according to the Variable of Average Monthly Household Income.

Level of significance	F-value	Mean of the squares	Degrees of freedom	Total squares	Source of the discrepancy	Variables
.076	2.310	.586	3	1.759	Between groups	Factors related to societal circumstances having a political stamp
		.254	408	103.515	Within groups	
			411	105.273	Total	
.822	.304	.092	3	.277	Between groups	Factors related to the organizations of the civil society
		.303	408	123.662	Within groups	
			411	123.938	Total	
.059	2.500	1.150	3	3.449	Between groups	Factors related to the university
		.460	408	187.638	Within groups	
			411	191.087	Total	
.078	2.286	1.426	3	4.279	Between groups	Factors related to the family
		.624	408	254.559	Within groups	
			411	258.838	Total	
.624	.587	.184	3	.553	Between groups	Factors related to the individual
		.314	408	128.013	Within groups	
			411	128.566	Total	

Table (13) shows that the significance level is higher than that required in the study ($\alpha \leq 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted, indicating that there are no statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the responses of the study sample regarding the factors influencing the formation of political awareness

toward participation in general national elections, as attributed to the variable of average monthly household income.

The researcher attributes this finding to the fact that monthly household income is no longer a decisive factor influencing political awareness or voter turnout, given the social and economic changes

that have helped narrow the gaps between individuals in terms of access to information and interest in public affairs. The widespread availability of media and social media has provided relatively equal opportunities for different economic groups to learn about political issues and follow current events, leading to a convergence in levels of political awareness regardless of income level. This result can also be explained by the fact that general national issues affect all segments of society without exception, which strengthens individuals' sense of belonging and shared responsibility, and means that political participation is not directly linked to economic capacity. In addition, cultural, educational, and social affiliations may play a more influential role than economic factors in shaping political

awareness and guiding electoral behavior. Consequently, monthly household income did not emerge as a variable explaining differences in the level of political awareness or electoral participation, but rather is part of a broader system of interrelated factors that contribute to shaping individuals' political attitudes and behavior.

The results of the sixth hypothesis, which states: There is no statistically significant relationship at a significance level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the factors influencing the formation of political awareness and participation in national general elections attributable to the variable of parents' educational level.

To test this hypothesis, I used a one-way ANOVA, as shown in Table 14.

Table (14): Results of the One-Way ANOVA For the Study Sample's Responses Regarding the Factors Influencing the Formation of Political Awareness Toward Participation in National General Elections, according to the Variable of Parents' Educational Level.

Level of significance	F-value	Mean of the squares	Degrees of freedom	Total squares	Source of the discrepancy	Variables
.463	.771	.198	2	.395	Between groups	Factors related to societal circumstances having a political stamp
		.256	409	104.878	Within groups	
			411	105.273	Total	
.411	.892	.269	2	.538	Between groups	Factors related to the organizations of the civil society
		.302	409	123.400	Within groups	
			411	123.938	Total	
.550	.599	.279	2	.558	Between groups	Factors related to the university
		.466	409	190.529	Within groups	
			411	191.087	Total	
.057	2.877	1.795	2	3.591	Between groups	Factors related to the family
		.624	409	255.247	Within groups	
			411	258.838	Total	
.061	2.823	.875	2	1.750	Between groups	Factors related to the individual
		.310	409	126.815	Within groups	
			411	128.566	Total	

Table (14) shows that the significance level is higher than that required in the study ($\alpha \leq 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted, indicating that there are no statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the responses of the study sample regarding the factors influencing the formation of political awareness toward participation in general national elections, attributable to the variable of parents' educational level.

The researcher attributes this finding to the fact that parents' educational level is no longer a decisive factor in shaping their children's political awareness or influencing their participation in elections, given the cognitive and social transformations taking place in society. Individuals have come to rely more heavily on diverse sources of information, foremost among them the media and social media, which have contributed to the formation of political awareness

that is relatively independent of the traditional family environment. This finding can also be explained by the fact that educational institutions, at all levels, play a significant role in developing students' political awareness, thereby compensating for potential differences resulting from variations in parents' educational levels. Furthermore, the nature of general national issues and their direct relevance to individuals' lives contribute to creating a sense of shared concern, regardless of the family's educational background. Consequently, the influence of parents' educational level appears limited compared to other more influential factors, such as the educational environment, broader socialization, and engagement in the digital sphere, which collectively contribute more clearly to shaping individuals' attitudes toward political participation.

Recommendations of the study in light of its findings:

1. The need to strengthen the role of educational institutions, particularly universities, in fostering political awareness among students by incorporating concepts of political participation and elections into the curriculum, as well as by promoting student activities that encourage constructive political dialogue and debate.
2. The researcher emphasizes the importance of positively leveraging the media and social media, given their significant role in shaping political awareness among various segments of society, and working to guide them toward spreading a culture of democratic participation and reinforcing national values.
3. The need to support community initiatives targeting young people, as they are the segment most affected and most capable of bringing about change, through awareness and training programs aimed at enhancing their participation in political life.
4. The researcher calls for the integration of efforts between official and civil society institutions in promoting political awareness, so that the role is not limited to a single entity but is part of a comprehensive national framework that seeks to build a political culture based on awareness and responsibility.
5. The researcher suggests conducting further studies that address other variables that may have a greater impact on shaping political awareness, such as party affiliation, level of media exposure, and the nature of the cultural and social environment, with the aim of gaining a deeper understanding of the factors influencing political participation.
6. The researcher recommends working to create a political environment that encourages participation by strengthening trust in the electoral process and ensuring transparency and integrity, thereby contributing to increased voter turnout in national elections.

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